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**PRINCIPLES OF GOOD CLINICAL PRACTICE IN RESTORATIVE AND
AESTHETIC DENTISTRY - POSSIBILITIES, PROBLEMS AND
SOLUTIONS**

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**PRINCIPLES OF GOOD CLINICAL PRACTICE IN ORAL SURGERY AND
REGENERATIVE DENTISTRY - POSSIBILITIES, PROBLEMS AND
SOLUTIONS**

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GENERAL ANESTHESIA IN DENTAL INTERVENTION IN CHILDREN

Anna Uram-Benka, Goran Rakić

Abstract

Dental treatment is one of the most common reasons for administering general anesthesia to children. Children's perception of pain is related to cognitive development. General anesthesia should be adapted to the kind and length of intervention, to the physical condition of the patients and to the fact that majority of these interventions are performed under the „one day surgery“ circumstances. The anesthetics initially used and those to maintain anesthesia must be short-active with minimal side-effects. The standard for the airway protection is endotracheal tube. In the postoperative period patients are given analgetics and other symptomatic therapy. The patients can be released no sooner than four hours after dental interventions.

Conclusion – An appropriate preoperative preparation and the selection of the adequate kind of general anesthesia result in a safety dental intervention in children in general anesthesia.

Introduction

Dental treatment is one of the most common reasons for administering general anaesthesia to children. In children, these procedures are often associated with a significant amount of pain and anxiety, for which pharmacological behaviour management is required.

Children's perception of pain is related to cognitive development. Before the age of 2 yr, a child is generally unable to distinguish between pressure and pain. Between the ages of 2 and 10 yr, a child may be able to understand the sensation of pain and differentiate it from other sensations such as pressure or vibration. Many dental procedures will still require general anesthesia in this age group. Children over the age of 10 yr may therefore be able to cooperate with dental treatment performed under local anesthesia, with or without sedation.

Indications for general anesthesia

General anesthesia may be required for paediatric dentistry in circumstances where:

- the use of local anesthesia is either contraindicated
- there has been previous failure of local anesthesia or sedation
- the patient is unable to cooperate with the proposed treatment due to immaturity, disability, or language difficulties;
- the patient suffers from a psychological disorder such as severe anxiety
- extensive treatment is required.

General anesthesia for paediatric dentistry should only be administered within a hospital setting. The necessary equipment is the standard for dental intervention as well as for the use of general anesthesia in children (oxygen source gases, anesthesia machine, monitoring, drugs, all necessary equipment for resuscitation etc.).

Preoperative preparation

Children who require general anaesthesia for dental treatment should receive the same standard of care as those who require general anesthesia for any other procedure. As for all episodes of paediatric anesthesia, the aim should be to ensure that the child is in the best possible physical and psychological condition to undergo the dental procedure. All children who require intervention under general anesthesia should be a healthy 14 days before intervention without antibiotic therapy (except if the disease is requiring). The day before the procedure should be accessed by the anesthesiologist to take history, get information about previous illnesses, operations and allergies. In the case of healthy children and small dental interventions, laboratory tests are not necessary as well as standard preoperative hematological and biochemical investigations. In case of any comorbidity laboratory analysis should be extended towards the disease, but it is also necessary to do preoperative examination by the physician-specialists.

Physical examination, measurement of vital parameters and advice for preoperative hygienic-dietary regime is important. On the day of surgery anesthesiologist also once again review the child and administer premedication.

Premedication

Premedication should be administered per orally, intramuscularly or intravenously. Premedication with oral analgetic agents is useful for the treatment of pain associated with paediatric dentistry. Many paediatric dental patients require sedative premedication. Midazolam is the most commonly used benzodiazepine. Atropine should be administered intramuscularly for optimum condition for the dental intervention (antisialagogue effect).

Induction and maintenance of anesthesia

Whenever general anesthesia is administered, clinical observation of the patient should be supplemented by core standards of monitoring that allow the physiological state of the patient, the depth of anesthesia, and the function of the anesthetic equipment to be assessed. These standards of monitoring should be uniform irrespective of the duration, location, or mode of general anesthesia. The induction of general anesthesia may occur via the inhalation route typically using sevoflurane, or the i.v. route, using an agent such as propofol with or without opioids and neuromuscular agents (rocuronium or cisatracurium). Airway protection can be by the oral placement of endotracheal tube. The nasal route is preferred by some dental surgeons. After tracheal intubation, a throat pack is usually inserted to protect the airway from soiling. A laryngeal mask airway (LMA) is often used for longer procedures, such as surgical extraction of impacted teeth. Displacement of the LMA may occur after insertion of the throat. Maintenance of anesthesia can be inhalatory or intravenous with oxygenation with air/oxygen, or nitrous-oxide/oxygen.

Uncomplicated dental extractions and other short dental procedures are usually associated with levels of pain that are adequately treated with paracetamol, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents (NSAIDs), or both. These may be administered before operation, intraoperatively, or after operation. Anti-emetic agents, such as ondansetron, dexamethasone, may be indicated and should always be considered whenever opioid analgesics are administered.

After completion of the procedure and removal of the throat pack, suction should be applied to the oropharynx. Residual neuromuscular block should be appropriately reversed, and 100% oxygen administered. The patient should then be placed in the left lateral position. The tracheal tube or LMA should be removed with the patient breathing spontaneously either awake or deeply anesthetized and when the patient's respiratory and laryngeal reflexes are returned, so that blood and secretions are less likely to be aspirated into the larynx. In the period immediately after general anesthesia for dental treatment, the child should be managed in an appropriately equipped post-anesthetic care unit by a designated member of staff who has received training in paediatric resuscitation. Supplemental oxygen should be administered until emergence from anesthesia has occurred.

Complications associated with general anesthesia for dental treatment

Minor complications of general anesthesia for paediatric dentistry include postoperative headache, nausea, retching, and vomiting, particularly in the presence of swallowed blood. Postoperative cough may occur due to either tracheal intubation or irritation from the throat-pack. Major complications include laryngospasm, bronchospasm, airway obstruction, cardiac arrhythmia and allergic reactions. These complications should be prevented, recognized and treated at the time. Therefore, it is necessary to have adequate equipment, drugs and qualified personnel for the implementation of general anesthesia in children.

Conclusion

The management of anxiety and pain is a very important aspect of paediatric dentistry and includes the use of general anesthesia. Adequate preoperative assessment, the choice of anesthetic technique, equipment and professional team ensure that these interventions are carried out safely in children.

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